

Chronic Kidney Disease and its Complications

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Abstract

High quality epidemiological studies conducted in different regions of the world revealed that at present 12 to 13% adult individuals have chronic kidney disease markers. The young population is prone to this complex disease at a very high rate. The progression of CKD is linked with the already existing a number of complications like diabetes, cardiovascular disease, hyperlipidemia, anemia and metabolic disorders. In CKD, the patient's kidneys fail to filter the blood at normal rate and this leads to accumulation of waste materials in the body and toxicity. If CKD isn't treated well on time, then it increases the morbidity and mortality rate. A multidisciplinary approach is required to combat this situation, especially in the developing countries like Pakistan, where resources are limited and healthcare institutes fail to provide adequate dialysis and patient management as per recommended guidelines. This review paper throws light on the chronic disease and its complications.

Keywords: Chronic Kidney Disease

Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is recognized as a major health problem affecting almost every nation around the globe. The number of patients with CKD is estimated to rise in the coming years, reflecting the rising cases of diabetes and hypertension in the elderly population. As the CKD cases rise, the health professionals will confront with the management of the complex medical problems. CKD is a complex disease and difficult to handle. Nephrologists rarely manages the medical needs of the patients with CKD until renal replacement is required.

In this paper, different stages of CKD and five major complications associated with it are discussed; anemia, nutrition, hyperlipidemia, osteodystrophy and cardiovascular risks.

Stages/ Classification of CKD

When kidney functioning is decreased and albumin is excreted in the abnormal quantities then the glomerular filtration rate is also abruptly affected, ¹ if this situation persists for more than three months then kidney began to damage and the condition is called as CKD. ^{2,3} In 24 hour urine collection, creatinine clearances and serum creatinine concentrations can be measured to estimate GFR. Both complications and risks for the progression of end stage renal disease require renal replacement therapy and this is more likely to occur in severe CKD patients. ⁴ However, early intervention and identification will likely reduce serious CKD sequelae and will reduce its progression. The National Kidney Foundation developed a criteria to facilitate CKD assessment and its severity. On the basis of this criteria, CKD is divided into the following stages:

- Stage 1: Persistent albuminuria and normal eGFR ≥ 90 mL/min per 1.73 m²
- Stage 2: eGFR between 60 to 89 mL/min per 1.73 m²
- Stage 3: eGFR between 30 to 59 mL/min per 1.73 m²
- Stage 4: eGFR between 15 to 29 mL/min per 1.73 m²

- Stage 5: eGFR of < 15 mL/min per 1.73 m² or end-stage renal disease

The progress of CKD from stage 2 to 3 and 4 moves toward end-stage renal disease at approximately 0.5% rate per year. ⁵

- **Chronic Kidney Disease Associated Anemia**

Anemia is a condition in which one or more of the major red blood cell measurements began to reduce at a very sharp rate; hemoglobin concentration, red blood cell count, or hematocrit. Anemia is defined by the World Health Organization as the level of hemoglobin less than 13 g/dL in men and post-menopausal women, and less than 12 g/dL in pre-menopausal women. It is defined by NKF as the level of hemoglobin less than 12.0 g/dL in women and less than 13.5 g/dL in men. ⁶

A normocytic, normochromic anemia usually comes up with CKD as it progresses, and the overall prevalence chances of anemia owing to CKD in patients are approximately 50%. Upon careful examination and follow-up anemia can be detected at its early stage in CKD patients, but a strong association has been found upon research with the severity of CKD and prevalence of anemia. One quarter of patients at stage 1 of CKD, half of patients at stage 2, 3, and 4, and three quarters of CKD patients at initial dialysis stage suffer from anemia. Therefore, it is the utmost duty of primary care providers to look out for any signs and symptoms for diagnosing and managing anemia in CKD patients. ⁷

Multiple mechanisms like iron, folate, vitamin B12 deficiency, gastrointestinal bleeding, systemic inflammation, severe hyperparathyroidism, shortened red blood cell survival and internal bleedings, can result in anemia associated with CKD. Moreover, decreased erythropoietin synthesis is the most specific and important etiology causing anemia in CKD patients. Kidney interstitial fibroblasts secrete erythropoietin, which is a glycoprotein. It is extremely important for the differentiation and growth of red blood cells in the bone marrow. Renal erythropoietin synthetic capacity is compromised in CKD, where tubular atrophy generates tubulointerstitial fibrosis and results in anemia. ^{8,9}

Morbidity and mortality are increased owing to anemia in CKD patients which further leads to other complications like angina, LVH, and heart failure. These conditions collectively further lead to deterioration of renal failure and a vicious cycle is established termed as “cardiorenal anemia syndrome”. If LVH is present in CKD patients, then the survival rate of patients on dialysis further decreases. In fact, patients with LVH and end-stage renal disease have 30% less survival rate than patients without LVH. Moreover, anemia itself alone is an independent predictor of death in stable coronary artery disease in CKD patients.

- **CKD Linked Mineral and Bone Disorders**

Abnormality in bone and mineral metabolism and/ or in extra skeletal calcification can occur as a secondary issue in CKD patients. Renal osteodystrophy is a histological set of changes which occurs in the bones of CKD patients. For phosphate excretion and 1- α -hydroxylation of vitamin D, kidney is the primary source. Hyperphosphatemia develops in CKD patients due to inadequate 1, 25 dihydroxy vitamin D levels, which reflects the reduced synthesis from parenchymal scarring. Moreover, renal phosphate excretion is also reduced. Both these processes together lead to serum calcium levels to fall and a rise in parathyroid hormone secretion. This hormone has a phosphaturic effect. It also increases the bone resorption and rises the calcium level by promoting 1- α -hydroxylation of 25-hydroxy vitamin D synthesized by the liver. In stage 3, increasing phosphorous levels in blood are universally observed. However, when eGFRs have declined below 50 mL/min per 1.73 m², then phosphate binder therapy is needed by the patients because secondary hyperthyroidism often starts to interrupt and distort the bone architecture long before the abnormal serum phosphorus levels can be detected. ^{10,11}

Bone disorders associated with CKD can increase mortality rate in the patients. In fact, hyperphosphatemia is one of the most important defining risk factor linked to CVD in CKD patients. The exact mechanism is ambiguous, but it is observed that hyperparathyroidism and vascular calcification results from high phosphorus levels. Excessive vitamin D therapy and calcium base binders' usage can also lead to vascular calcification and its attendant cardiovascular mortality.

In addition to phosphate binders, many other drug classes have been developed to handle CKD linked mineral disorder. Failing kidney reduced the 1- hydroxylation of vitamin D so vitamin D related compounds might be required to raise serum calcium concentration which in turn suppresses parathyroid hormone secretion. Agents like calcimimetics can also be given to the patients which rises the calcium sensitivity of the calcium sensitive receptors. These receptors are expressed by the parathyroid glands.¹²

• Cardiovascular Risk

CVD mortality rates are one in every 10 patients and this is an alarming factor. Renal impairment increases the CVD risks as the kidney disease progresses. There are strong evidences that mild to strong renal impairment levels are linked with increased cardiovascular risks. Hypertension is a traditional factor known for leading to CVD. Systolic blood pressure is more strongly associated with the CVD and death in patients who underwent dialysis, than diastolic or pulse pressure.

However, a U shaped relationship has been found between mortality rate and systolic blood pressure in which low or high pressure seems to be associated with increased death rate in CKD stage 5 patients. Multiple guidelines recommend target blood pressure less than 130/85 mm Hg for patients suffering from kidney disease and less than 125/75 mm Hg for patients with urinary protein excretion higher than 1g/24h. Detailed treatment recommendations are beyond the scope of this paper. ACE (angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors) or receptor blockers, these kind of agents are used as optimal first line agents in proteinuric patients.¹³

• Dyslipidemia

Lipid profile varies widely in CKD patients. The stage of disease defines the varying degree of lipid profile. Generally, the hyperlipidemia profile increases with the progression of kidney disease, and LDL & cholesterol levels elevate according to the severity of renal impairment.

Several factors contribute to the occurrence of dyslipidemia. CKD patients faces a reduction in hepatic triglyceride lipase and lipoprotein lipase activity. This interferes with the uptake of apolipoproteinB and triglyceride rich lipoproteins by the peripheral tissues and the liver. This leads to increased level of circulation of atherogenic lipoproteins. In nephritic syndrome, hypercholesterolemia is thought to be owing to decreased catabolism and increased lipoprotein production. The degree of abnormality is roughly linked with the proteinuria amount and inversely with the serum albumin level.^{14,15}

Moreover, dextran and infusion of albumin both contributes in normalizing the concentration of lipoproteins which in turn impacts the oncotic pressure and increases the signals for lipoprotein synthesis by the liver. In vitro experiments have demonstrated that increased hepatic apolipoprotein-B egen transcription in cells which are exposed to reduced oncotic pressure are directly stimulated by the later.

Specific K/DOQI guidelines on the management of hyperlipidemia include:

1. For patients with cholesterol levels/ LDL between 100 and 129 mg/dL change in lifestyle may be the initial therapy. If target LDL levels are not achieved (LDL < 100 mg/dL [2.57 mmol/L]), low-dose statin therapy can be instituted.
2. For patients with LDL \geq 130 mg/dL, lifestyle changes alone are not effective for the positive results. Statins can be used as initial therapy and the dose titrated to achieve target LDL < 100 mg/dL.

3. For patients with TG \geq 200 mg/dL, the goal is to achieve non-HDL cholesterol \leq 130 mg/dL. Initial treatment includes lifestyle changes plus a low dose statin which is increased as per need to achieve target levels. ^{16,17}

• Nutritional Issues

As the CKD stages progresses, the nutritional requirements also changes and metabolism of protein, water, potassium, salt and phosphorous are also effected. these undesirable changes causes ineffective energy generation despite adequate intake of diet. In more extreme cases, it can cause uremic malnutrition. It is a syndrome which is distinctive from that one which arises owing to insufficient dietary intake.

Uremic malnutrition and its association with the CKD can not be observed in the early stages. However, poor pre-dialysis can effect the nutritional status of the patients and can directly influence and increase the patient's morbidity and mortality rate after the renal replacement therapy is initiated.

It is mandatory to assess nutritional status in CKD patient to address their nutritional needs in a handsome manner. Serum albumin is one of the most extensively studied nutritional marker which is easily available and has strong linkage with hospitalization and risk of death. Low serum albumin levels indicated that patients have poor clinical outcomes in all stages of CKD. recommend maintenance of a value of 4.0 g/dL or greater for serum albumin in stage 5 CKD patients is recommended by the clinicians. ¹⁸

Conclusion:

CKD patients face multiple complexities that can lead to severe health issues and increased mortality and morbidity rates. The staging system which was introduced in 2002 is quite helpful for proper identification and management of these complications in CKD patients. With on time identification and treatment of anemia, renal osteodystrophy, CVD, uremic malnutrition and other issues in the lives of the patients can be significantly improved.

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